

**Perceived organisational support, job involvement and turnover intention in
lean production in Sri Lanka**

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Abstract

The literature suggests that the bottom-line changes often cited in lean implementation success stories, such as reduced inventories and faster flow times, are not the only results that should be considered. The potential detrimental effects on employees should be considered as well, or turnover and morale problems may sabotage the effectiveness of such implementations. However, the ways in which lean production environment influence employee behavior has received scant empirical attention. The aim of this paper is to examine the mediating effect of job involvement on the relationship between perceived organizational support and turnover intention in the lean production in Sri Lanka. A random sample of 616 shop-floor employees engaged full-time in export-apparel manufacturing firms that have implemented a formal lean production system in the whole manufacturing function and it has become the standard of operation for at least one year in Sri Lanka responded. Regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses. It was found that job involvement partially mediates the relationship between perceived organizational support and turnover intention. The findings provide useful information to better understand employee perceptions toward lean production environment and the findings will be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

***Key words:** job involvement, lean production, perceived organizational support, turnover intention.*

1 Introduction

Lean production is identified as a radical process innovation that is not restricted to its origin [1] in the auto industry, but has wide applicability in many different countries and industries [2]. The literature identifies lean production as a bundle of associated practices installed as a system, such as total quality management, just-in-time, and continuous improvement [3-7]. Some authors include human resource management as another associated practice that facilitate or limit the adoption of lean production [e.g. 6, 8-9].

The reorganisation of manufacturing processes according to lean production requirements trigger techno-organisational changes with a new strategy, structure, and the social organisation of work system [8, 10]. For instance, lean production dependent on several core characteristics such as the multiskilling of workforce, broadening of job boundaries, consolidation of departments, and commitment to team-based work organisation [11]. Therefore, some scholars argue that human factor alone can differentiate firms who are successful in the adoption from those that are not so successful [8]. Although firms can gain benefits such as quality improvements and cost reductions by restructuring work systems for the lean production, several scholars criticise the work systems of lean production for being exploitative and high pressure to shop-floor employees [2, 12]. Therefore, when capturing and capitalising on individual capabilities in the lean production, there is a need to better understand work related attitudes of employees.

Empirical research on human resource aspects and lean production effects in the South Asian operations environment is sparse and therefore understanding employees' perceptions towards work systems of lean production is important for several reasons. First, although scholars identify lean production as an important subfield of operations management for further inquiry and understanding [13] few research studies were devoted to understand the human dimension in the lean production [e.g. 10, 14-16]. Second, scholars find that the utilisation of advanced manufacturing technologies is associated with a greater reliance on non-financial performance measures [e.g. 17, 18]. In this regards, organisational behaviour literature identifies employee work attitudes as one of such non-financial performance measures [19]. However, our review of literature has shown that employee beliefs and attitudes to various dimensions of new manufacturing

management initiatives have so far gone largely unrecorded. To date, few case studies [e.g. 16, 20-22], quantitative questionnaire surveys [e.g. 8, 14, 15] and a qualitative interview survey [e.g. 23] attempted to address human dimension in the lean production. Therefore, there is no consensus regarding the extent to which, and ways in which, the adoption of lean production has implications for human resources on the shop-floor [2].

Third, within the organisational behaviour literature, behavioural scientists pointing to the evidence of lack of commitment, low job satisfaction, and restriction of productivity in traditional plants have argued for increased opportunities for employees to participate at work [24]. Subsequent research within the organisational behaviour literature provides support that job involvement reduces turnover intention [e.g. 25, 26]. However, employee job involvement is an integral aspect of a successful lean production process [14, 15, 18]. For instance, previous research [see 27] showed empirically that characteristics such as completeness of the work, difficulty of the work, monotony of the work, workplace autonomy, interaction potential in the work, presence of organizing tasks, and information provision (on time, complete and reliable) with respect to the work to be done are important determinants of quality of working life in the lean production environment. However, the literature concerning the characteristics of work organization in lean production and its impact on employees is not quite clear [see 28]. On one hand, the proponents of lean production suggest that workers in lean production settings appear to display intrinsically motivated, internally driven and more productive than in traditional assembly line settings, which has been linked to improved manufacturing outcomes and competitiveness [e.g. 1]. On the other hand, the opponents of lean production argue that it places workers in highly limiting and alienating

conditions [see 28]. For instance, Vidal [23] suggests that when participatory work arrangements involve substantial new responsibilities employees may experience those as burdens rather than challenges, and an increased level of employee job involvement does not necessarily increase their job satisfaction. In a similar vein, Brown and Mitchell [29] found that human related performance obstacles in the work environment that prevent people from performing their jobs to the best of their abilities had increased in the importance after the implementation of just-in-time (JIT). As employees in the JIT system are highly dependent on other group members, they perceived greater obstacles than the batch employees in the area of reliance on co-workers [29]. Hence, Brown and Mitchell [29] conclude that the bottom-line changes often cited in JIT success stories, such as reduced inventories and faster flow times, are not the only results that should be considered. The potential for detrimental effects on employees should be considered as well, or turnover and morale problems may sabotage the effectiveness of JIT implementation. On the contrary, Schouteten and Benders [27] showed empirically that although many assembly workers had reported rather low job satisfaction and commitment, relative to these levels they had reported low intention to resign. Therefore, our review of literature suggests that the impact of the lean production implementation on employees' behaviour is not quite clear. There is surprisingly little empirical research addressing human dimension in the operations management literature. Our review of journals that are outlets for operations management related research in popular databases of Business Source Premier, ABI/Inform, Emerald, ScienceDirect, Springer, and Wiley Blackwell has not been able to find studies that are conducted on perceived organisational support (POS), job involvement, and turnover intention in the lean production context. Therefore, it is expected that the findings of this study would be able to

provide useful information to better understand employee perceptions towards lean production environment. Further, it is expected that the findings of this study will be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Finally, the literature on operations management themes describes application contexts in North America, Western Europe as well as countries in the Asia-Pacific region such as Australia and Japan. However, valuable lessons could be learned from implementation experiences in different parts of the world, especially in South Asia. In response to several factors, such as increasing global competition, low labour costs in Sri Lanka and inducements from the Sri Lankan government, the number of international businesses coming into the country has been increasing. In the context of globalisation of business operations and interlocking supply chains, a research on lean production systems in South Asia [Sri Lanka in particular] is interesting, relevant and timely since relatively little is known about human resource aspects of operations management contexts in this part of the world.

In the above context, the purpose of this paper is to examine the associations between POS, job involvement and turnover intention in the lean production in Sri Lanka. With regard to the treatment of POS, job involvement and turnover intention in previous studies, these variables have been treated as independent, dependent, moderator and mediator variables depending on the purpose of the study. For instance, POS is treated as an independent variable [e.g. 30] and a mediator variable [e.g. 31, 32]; job involvement is treated as an independent variable [e.g. 33] and a moderator [e.g. 34]; and turnover intention is treated as a mediator [e.g. 35] and a dependent variable [e.g. 33]. The current study treats POS as an independent variable, turnover intention as a dependent variable, and job involvement as a mediator in the lean production in Sri Lanka. In

other words, by taking into account how POS affects job involvement and how job involvement in turn impacts on employees' turnover intention, the study tested the role of job involvement as a mediator between POS and turnover intention [refer to Figure 1]. For the study, the quantitative research methodology was used and collected data from 616 shop-floor employees full-time engaged in export-apparel manufacturing firms that have implemented lean production systems in Sri Lanka. It is expected that the understanding of sources and consequences of job involvement would be of considerable interest, both theoretically and practically. Consistent with the objective, the next section briefly describes the Sri Lankan context and reviews the theoretical background of the study. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Thereafter, the main findings are presented and discussed. The article concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

2 Background of the study: Sri Lankan context

The export-apparel manufacturing industry is the leading manufacturing industry in Sri Lanka that has emerged as the country's main export earner and the largest single employment provider in the industrial sector [36]. When producing apparel for the developed countries in the West, local manufactures have to strictly adhere to product design specifications provided by the foreign buyer, such as Marks and Spencer, who defines product design and quality.

The growth witnessed by this industry can be attributed to two major factors. First, the market-oriented liberal economic policies introduced in 1977 [37]. Second, the Multi-Fibre Agreement (MFA), the worldwide system of managed trade in textiles and apparel that came into existence in 1974 (which subsequently integrated into the World Trade Organisation framework by 2005).

The MFA introduced a quota system for the export of apparel products to developed countries by limiting the quantity of garments that can be exported by the developing countries to any single developed country. Therefore, the quota holding apparel exporting developing countries had been ensured a guaranteed market.

Due to rising wages and quota restrictions by MFA on East Asian economies [such as Hong Kong, South Korea and Taiwan, who were the leaders in apparel export by late 1970s], export-apparel production shifted to quota holding Asian countries, such as Sri Lanka, Thailand, Philippines, Indonesia, China, India, and Pakistan in the late 1970s. Thereafter, the export-apparel production has, further, shifted to quota holding other countries with relatively lower labour cost in Asia [such as Laos, Cambodia, Bangladesh, and Vietnam], Latin and Central America, Caribbean, Eastern Europe, and North Africa [37, p 255]. Overall, under the quota regime, Sri Lanka like other apparel exporting developing countries had enjoyed relatively assured export market through bilateral agreements with the developed world.

However, changes occurred when this system of managed trade perpetrated by MFA came to an end. The World Trade Organisation, which replaced GATT ushers a restriction-free world trade, set out a time period of 10 years from 1995 to 2005 for the phase-out of MFA quota system and the integration of textiles and apparel export trade into the WTO framework. Export-apparel manufacturing industry in Sri Lanka faced this imminent phase-out of MFA quota system for the EU by late 1990s and for the USA (and other Western countries) in 2005. In real terms phasing out of the quota system challenged the very foundation on which this industry was built. Since the phase-out of the quota system by 2005, apparel exporting countries from Asia, Latin and Central

America, Caribbean, Eastern Europe, and North Africa have been competing intensively with each other for the market share. Since then, other competitive dimensions such as productivity and quality, therefore, come on centre stage. This change of priorities has influenced to rethink operations management strategies adopted in this sector.

Since mid 2000s, export-apparel manufacturers in Sri Lanka identified possibilities for them to turn to lean production for improving the efficiency of production systems. Scholars also suggest that rapid change industries adopt lean production as a growth paradigm [e.g. 38, 39]. The attributes of lean production [see 1, 2, 40], such as integrated, single piece production flow, low inventory, and close integration from raw material to customer through partnership fit in high-volume repetitive export-apparel manufacturing environment in Sri Lanka.

Preliminary investigations made by us revealed that export-apparel manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka are changing their production methods and management practices to become leaner and fitter to suit the new production model (also refer to Appendix).

When considering the shop-floor workforce of this industry, workforce statistics [36, 41] and past studies [42] report that a majority of shop-floor employees are female, single, less than 25 years of age, and have secondary education less than or equal to 10 years of full-time education. Further, employees belong to any category of the workforce of this industry are not unionised.

However, it should be noted that the State interventions to protect the interests of the workers who do not have equal bargaining power with the employers has resulted in the enactment of a large number of labour statutes, where some argues that the Sri Lankan labour legislation is over protective of employees and weigh heavily in favour of them [43]. The platform indeed for the industry is better

educated and trained employees; employers expect them to stay longer in a job. However, the industry suffers with a monthly average turnover rate of 8% for shop-floor employees. Therefore, when capturing and capitalising on individual capabilities, there is a need to better understand work related attitudes of employees. Further, being in the export-apparel manufacturing industry for more than 30 years, the findings of this study will provide valuable information to both academics and practitioners as it is scarce to find empirical evidence on human dimension in the lean production.

3 Theoretical background and hypotheses

3.1 Perceived organizational support

Perceived organisational support captures an employee's beliefs concerning the extent to which the organisation values (employees') general contributions made on the organisation's behalf and cares for their well-being [44]. In other words, POS focuses on the employer's side of the exchange as perceived by employees. Therefore, an employee's beliefs of how an organisation values him or her is vital for determining whether any attitudes or behaviours benefiting the organisation emerge from the exchange relationship that takes place between the employee and employer [45].

It has been argued that POS is affected by fair allocation of job rewards for the effort employees put in to meet organisational goals, which signify a belief that the organisation values the contributions of its employees [46]. Job rewards include tangible incentives, such as pay and fringe benefits and socio-emotional benefits such as esteem, supportive and helpful supervision, approval, and caring [45]. Further, employees value job rewards to be based on the discretion of the organisation rather than influenced by external forces, such as unions or health

and safety regulations [47]. These voluntary job rewards that come directly from the organisation are perceived as an indication that the organisation values employees' contributions made on the organisation's behalf and cares for their well-being [47].

Organisational behaviour literature provides evidence that employees with a higher level of POS are likely to reciprocate with positive feelings, job attitudes, and behavioural intentions towards the organisation [46]. Two of such job related outcomes are job involvement and turnover intention [46]. In developing an account of the relationships between POS, job involvement and turnover intention, in the following paragraphs, our focus is on specific literature that is relevant and useful for the current study. Further, for this study four hypotheses were developed as per the three-step procedure recommended by Baron and Kenny [48], which was used to test the mediation hypothesis (refer to the section on *data analysis procedure*).

3.2 Job involvement

The literature identifies job involvement as an individual's level of psychological identification with the specific job in which he or she is engaged or being absorbed in it [49]. Organisational behaviour literature suggests several different conceptualisations of job involvement [see also 33, 50], such as the degree of importance of one's job to one's self-image [e.g. 51]; the degree to which an individual's self-esteem or self-worth is affected by his or her perceived performance level [e.g. 52]; and the degree to which an individual is actively participating in his or her job [e.g. 53, 54]. Past researchers have adopted appropriate conceptualisations of job involvement depending on the purpose of their studies [e.g. 33, 34, 55]. Drawing from the previous research, for the

conceptual framework presented in this paper [refer to Figure 1], job involvement is referred to as the extent to which an individual is actively participating in his or her job. Saleh and Hosek [50] provide an extensive review of literature on this line of job involvement, where they synthesise:

...[an] interpretation of job involvement was proposed by Allport [53] who conceptualised it as the degree to which an employee is participating in his or her job and meeting such needs as prestige, self-respect, autonomy, and self-regard. A similar interpretation was given by Gurin et al. [56] in which they indicated that personal involvement in the job depends on the extent to which an individual seeks some self-expression and actualisation in his or her work. The same type of job involvement was suggested by Wickert [57] and Bass [54]. Bass [54], for instance, suggests that the opportunity to make job decisions, the feeling that one is making an important contribution to company success, the chance to set one's own work pace, and self determination lead to the strengthening of job involvement. Wickert [57] suggested that the participation type of involvement could be measured by asking the employee the degree to which he or she feels that he or she is actively participating in his or her job.” [p. 214].

Our main reason for adopting this interpretation of job involvement is that the literature on operations management, lean production in particular, identifies employee participation as an integral aspect of lean production [14, 15, 18], and employee job involvement is higher in lean production plants than in traditional plants [e.g. 8]. In the lean production setting, employee job involvement manifests itself in many forms, such as active participation in root cause problem solving,

the interruption of production flow whenever they notice anomalies or defects, the adaptation of work teams to variations in job duties in the production flow, the exchange of positions within the work group and the habit of “giving each other a hand” in moments of difficulty, and the commitment of each employee to the continuous improvement [see 16, 20, 22, 40, 58]. Overall, employee job involvement increases flexibility and reduces the vulnerability of the lean production system [8].

Although a majority of publications on lean production devotes some space to highlight the importance of employee job involvement, those are mainly focused on technical aspects [8, 10, 16]. Further, the treatment of recent important developments in manufacturing methods in the organisational behaviour literature remains partial because of its failure to engage fully with the operational arrangements [15, 16]. Therefore, there is a need to investigate antecedents to and consequences of job involvement [refer to Figure 1] in the operations management literature.

3.2.1 Perceived organizational support and job involvement

Previous research provides support for a significant direct positive relationship between POS and job involvement suggesting POS as an antecedent to job involvement [59, 60]. In the Sri Lankan context, Wickramasinghe [42] surveyed 284 shop-floor employees from 6 out of 12 export-apparel manufacturing firms that have implemented lean production systems and reported a significant positive correlation between POS and job involvement. Therefore, it is important to investigate employees’ perceptions towards POS and its possible outcomes, job involvement in particular. Consistent with the past research, it is hypothesized for this study:

Hypothesis 1. POS will be positively related to job involvement

3.3 Turnover intention

Turnover intention refers to whether an employee intends to leave his or her current place of employment [61]. Several past research have demonstrated that intention to leave is one of the strongest predictors and an immediate precursor of employee turnover [62, 63].

3.3.1 Job involvement and turnover intention

The findings of past research within the organisational behaviour literature suggest that a high level of job involvement is an inherently desirable attribute of employees. The highly job involved individuals seem to be satisfied with their jobs, in characteristic positive moods at work and record regular attendance and punctuality at work [25]. These highly job involved employees believe that personal and organisational goals are compatible and rarely think about quitting their jobs and expect to be working for the same organisation in the foreseeable future [25, 26]. Overall, previous research from non-lean production settings provides evidence that job involvement is associated with significant improvements in the quality of work life of employees. The past studies in the context of lean production provide evidence that job involvement through solving production problems and devising process improvements can increase job control by providing off-line opportunities to utilise a higher level of skills and to improve job tasks and product quality [e.g. 8]. However, Vidal [23] suggests that employees in lean production may find involvement not only brings substantial new responsibilities but also brings pressures and psychological tensions, which could be experienced as burdens rather than challenges [23]. However, Wickramasinghe [42] provides evidence for the existence of significant negative

correlation between job involvement and turnover intention in the lean production in Sri Lanka. Therefore, a detailed exploration of the linkage between these variables in the lean production would be of considerable interest, both theoretically and practically. Therefore, based on the empirical evidence that indicates job involvement significantly negatively related to turnover intention, for this study, it is hypothesized:

Hypothesis 2. Job involvement will be negatively related to turnover intention

3.3.2 Perceived organizational support and turnover intention

As POS reinforces employees' beliefs that the organisation values their contributions and cares about their well-being they are likely to reciprocate with positive attitudes and behavioural intentions [46]. Scholars also suggest that POS fulfils employees' socio-emotional needs [including approval, affiliation and self-esteem] and develops a sense of unity with the organisation, involving the incorporation of organisational membership into their social identity [59]. Therefore, employees with a high level of POS tend to express stronger feelings of affiliation and loyalty to their organisation [32] and reduce their intentions to leave the employing organisation [64]. Previous research, within organisational behaviour literature [e.g. 32, 35, 64] as well as in the context of lean production in Sri Lanka, Wickramasinghe, [42] provides evidence for a significant negative relationship between POS and turnover intention. However, there have been limited investigations on the relationship between POS and intention to leave [e.g. 32, 61, 64] and more empirical work has been called for [62]. Therefore, consistent with past research, it is hypothesized for this study:

Hypothesis 3. POS will be negatively related to turnover intention

As detailed in the section on introduction, previous research treated job involvement differently [e.g. independent variable by Blau and Boal (33), a moderator by Ruh et al., (32)] depending on the context of the study. In this regards, Cotton et al. [65] state the importance of considering antecedents, consequences, mediating process and contextual contingencies in analysing employee participation. In a similar vein, Abelson [66] and Wagner [67] suggest that small episodic effects can sometimes have strong cumulative consequences that may amass over time. Therefore, there is a need of a closer understanding of the dynamics of job involvement and the impact it has on the relationship between POS and turnover intention. Therefore, building on the previously reviewed literature, our study developed a model to explore whether job involvement mediates the relationship between POS and turnover intention. In that, we propose employees' beliefs that organisation values their contributions made on the organisation's behalf and cares for their well-being, termed POS, generates significantly positive attitudes towards job involvement, which in turn significantly reduces their turnover intention in the lean production context. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

Hypothesis 4. Job involvement will mediate the relationship between POS
and turnover intention

Figure 1 shows the proposed model.

Take in Figure 1

4 Methodology

4.1 Sample

The target population for the study is a cross section of shop-floor employees employed full-time in export-apparel manufacturing firms, which have implemented a formal lean production system in the whole manufacturing function and lean production has become the standard of operation for at least one year in Sri Lanka. Following sample selection criteria were set for the study: 1) a firm should be registered under the Board of Investment of Sri Lanka [BOI] as it is the primary government authority responsible for identifying, promoting and facilitating both foreign and local investments in the country and export-apparel manufacturing is the major industrial category under BOI [68]. Further, it is compulsory by law that all BOI-registered firms should export at least 90% of the manufactured output [68]. Thus, all export-apparel manufacturing firms that come under this study population are homogeneous in nature in terms of business operations; and 2) a firm should have implemented a formal lean production system in the whole manufacturing function (not as a pilot project) and it should be the standard of operation for at least one year. This criterion was set as past researchers [e.g. 69] suggested the importance of distinguishing firms that have implemented lean and firms that are planning to implement, etc. Although there are nearly 800 firms engaged in the export-apparel manufacturing industry, in mid 2008, Wickramasinghe [42] identified 12 BOI registered export-apparel manufacturing firms that had implemented lean production systems in their whole manufacturing function and has become the standard of operation for at least one year. These 12 firms were considered as the population frame for this study and all the firms agreed to participate in the survey. To fulfil the expectations of this study, it was decided to collect data from shop-floor employees. Twelve contact

persons were identified from each firm. The contact person from each firm together with one of the authors of this paper randomly selected shop-floor employees to be participated in this study. In doing so, attempts were made to select a cross-section of shop-floor employees from each firm. Further, participants were briefed about the aims of the study prior to the questionnaire distribution and their responses were anonymous. One thousand survey questionnaires were distributed among the firms covering at least 5% of the total shop-floor employees in each firm. Of the total number of questionnaires distributed, 625 responses received. 616 usable responses resulted in 62% response rate. This response rate is considered reasonable based on norms set for behavioural research [e.g. 70], where Baruch [70] provides a norm for response rate in academic studies in behavioural sciences as 60% +/- 20%.

With regard to the characteristics of responding firms, the oldest firm was established in the year 1993 while the youngest firm was established in the year 2004. All the firms have adopted lean production methods after 2005, where the latest adoption occurred in two of the firms in the year 2007. When the firm size is measured in terms of average annual turnover in US\$ and the number of people employed, the respondent firms had an average annual turnover [in US\$] ranged from 50 to 250 Million while the total number of employees ranged from 300 to 5000. All the firms had dedicated section to handle lean implementation headed by a senior level manager. Although we wanted to gather secondary data on the performance of lean production, only five firms provided some data while others refused to provide. The data obtained are given in Appendix. As shown in Appendix, two firms also provided some data for before versus after comparison. Although other participating firms did not provide these data, it does

not mean that they have not implemented the “lean production”. The characteristics of the sample are shown in Table 1.

Take in Table 1

4.2 Measures

Independent, dependent and mediator variables were measured using a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 [strongly disagree] to 5 [strongly agree]. In this regards, Kulas et al. [71] found that middle response category did not adversely affect reliability and validity in social research. For all measurement scales, standardized Cronbach’s alpha was examined and Principal-components factor analysis [Varimax rotation] was conducted. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7 [see 71]. The items of each factor were averaged to produce a mean score for the each construct [refer to Table 2].

Turnover intention was measured using the three item scale used by Hui et al. [35]. Example items include “I often think of leaving the organisation” and “it is very possible that I will look for a new job next year”. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardized Cronbach’s alpha=.705 Eigenvalue=2.432, and explained variation=71.23%.

Job involvement was measured by five items adapted from Vroom [73]. Example items include “I have much say and influence over what goes on in my job”, and “I have much chance to feel at the end of the day that I have

accomplished something”. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardized Cronbach’s alpha=.782, Eigenvalue=3.03, and explained variation=78.25%.

Perceived organisational support was measured using the eight-item short version of Eisenberger et al.’s [45] POS scale. An example item includes “Help is available from my organisation when I have a problem”. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardized Cronbach’s alpha=.760, Eigenvalue=2.895, and explained variation=73.16%.

Although we intend to control characteristics of lean production (e.g. the reduction of WIP, space, etc.), as mentioned earlier, the firms were reluctant to provide these data. Therefore, the duration of lean production was selected as a control variable. The literature also suggests that the extent to which firms have adopted a lean production system may influenced by the duration of lean production in operation [e.g. 4, 11, 15]. Therefore, the duration of lean production in operation, termed as “lean duration” in this study [in years], and five individual demographic characteristics (gender, marital status, education, age, and firm tenure) were controlled in the analysis. Of these individual demographic characteristics, gender [male=0, female=1], marital status [single=0, married=1] and the highest level of education [less than or equal to O/L=0, up to A/L=1] were binary coded while age and tenure were coded as continuous variables in years.

The measurement scales were previously used by Wickramasinghe [42] in his study [N=284] on Sri Lankan export-apparel manufacturing firms that have implemented lean production systems in Sri Lanka. Therefore, although the measures of constructs used in this study were developed in Western, English speaking countries these were used in our target industry in a previous study. Further, Wickramasinghe [42] reports that measurement scales obtained standardized Cronbach’s alpha values higher than 0.7, fulfilling the accepted

guidelines proposed by Hair et al. [72]. Since target respondents may not have a good command of English, self-administered survey questionnaire was in native language, *Sinhala*. We have used *Sinhala* translations of measurement scales from the study of Wickramasinghe [42], for two reasons. First, Wickramasinghe [42] assured the equivalence of the meaning of the measures that is used in native language as he adhered to guidelines stipulated in the literature [see 74]. Second, these item scales were previously successfully tested in the same industrial sector by Wickramasinghe [42] and found to be valid and reliable in the Sri Lankan context.

When self-report measures from a single source are used to evaluate variables, the literature highlights the problem of common method bias [75, 76]. However, Spector [76] suggests that despite the weaknesses of the cross-sectional self-report methodology, this design can be quite useful in providing a picture of and inter-correlations among people's job environment and their reactions to jobs, which can be useful for deriving hypotheses about how people react to jobs. Therefore, procedural and statistical measures were taken to reduce common method bias in the current study. First, the anonymity of the respondents was ensured to reduce evaluation apprehension [a procedure recommended by Podsakoff et al. (75)]. Second, factor analysis was used to conduct Harman's single-factor test; neither single factor emerged from this analysis nor was there a general factor that could account for the majority of variance fulfilling the recommended guidelines of Podsakoff et al. [75].

4.3 Data analysis procedure

Regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses. The three-step procedure recommended by Baron and Kenny [48] was used to test the mediation

hypothesis. According to Baron and Kenny [48], the following conditions must be met to support a mediating relationship. First, the independent variable must be significantly associated with the dependent variable. Second, the independent variable must be significantly associated with the mediator. Finally, after the mediator is entered, the relationship between the independent and dependent variables should either disappear [full mediation] or significantly diminish [partial mediation]. In addition to the above conditions set out by Baron and Kenny [48], Preacher and Leonardelli's [77] interactive programme was used to calculate critical ratios. To confirm the nature of the mediation relationship (full or partial), Jose's [78] Excel version of MedGraph programme was used.

5 Results

Table 2 shows means, standard deviations and zero-order correlations among the variables. It is apparent from Table 2 that job involvement significantly negatively associated with turnover intention as predicted in H2 [also refer to Table 3].

Further POS significantly positively associated with job involvement while POS significantly negatively associated with turnover intention.

Take in Table 2

In analysing the mediator effect of job involvement, the hypotheses were tested by estimating a series of multiple regression equations following the procedure presented in the section on *data analysis procedure*. The results are shown in Table 3. As can be seen in Table 3, the conditions for mediation were met. POS significantly positively associated with job involvement [$\beta = .419, p < .001$]. This supports H1. POS significantly negatively associated with turnover intention [$\beta = -$

.433, $p < .001$]. This supports H3. After job involvement is entered, the relationship between POS and turnover intention significantly diminishes [$\beta = -.433$, $p < .001$ to $\beta = -.234$, $p < .01$], suggesting partial mediation. The critical ratios obtained from Preacher and Leonardelli's [77] interactive programme are also shown in Table 3. In addition, standardized coefficients of POS on turnover intention revealing direct and indirect effects obtained from Jose's [78] MedGraph programme are also shown in Table 3. Accordingly, the mediation hypothesis (H4) that job involvement mediates the relationship between POS and turnover intention is supported by the data.

Take in Table 3

Overall, the study investigated one of the core characteristics of lean production, i.e., employee job involvement. In doing so, the study considered POS as an antecedent to job involvement [H1] and turnover intention [H3], and job involvement as an antecedent to turnover intention [H2]. As shown in Table 3, it was found that POS enhance job involvement of the employees in the lean production, and it in turn reduces their turnover intention [H4]. In other words, job involvement operates as a salient mediator in the relationship between POS and employee turnover intention.

6 Conclusions and implications

This article explored the mediating effect of job involvement on the relationship between POS and turnover intention. As job involvement and turnover intention are two aspects desired by employers in the lean production context, the findings presented in this paper would be of interest to both academics and practitioners.

We have used widely accepted multiple parameters drawn from the literature reviewed earlier to evaluate POS, job involvement and turnover intention. The item scales shown to be valid and reliable in the Sri Lankan context. This supports claims made by Wickramasinghe [42] that above measures seem to be valid and reliable in the Sri Lankan context.

The belief that the organisation cares about its employees and values their contribution, i.e., POS, was found to be positively associated with higher levels of job involvement. The significant positive relationship between POS and job involvement in this study lends credence to previous findings within the organisational behaviour literature [e.g. 45, 60]. Several past studies conclude that employee job involvement is a critical element of the lean production [see 18]. In the lean production, employees must participate in problem solving as decision making is decentralised to manage variance and uncertainty. Further, job involvement through participation gives higher ownership of the process to employees. The findings of the study imply that POS plays an important role in making employees more involved in their task accomplishment in the lean production. This finding has an implication to organisations. Employees in the lean production will increase the level of job involvement if they perceive that the organisation cares about its employees and values their contribution. Therefore, organisations have to visibly support employees. This can be done by fair allocation of job rewards for the effort employees put in to meet organisational goals. The job rewards can be given as pay and fringe benefits as well as socio-emotional benefits such as esteem, supportive and helpful supervision and approval.

Further, the findings are also inline with the findings of previous studies within the organisational behaviour literature that POS significantly reduces

turnover intention [e.g. 64]. The literature considers POS as the quality of exchange that takes place between an employee and the employer [see 44]. Therefore, the findings suggest that an employee who sees the employer as supportive is more likely to engage in reduced turnover intention. This also has an implication to organisations, i.e., visible support for employees not only increases job involvement of employees in the lean production environment but also reduces their turnover intention.

Furthermore, we found that job involvement significantly negatively related to turnover intention. Our finding of an inverse relationship between job involvement and turnover intention is consistent with previous research within the organisational behaviour literature [e.g. 25, 26]. However, the influence of job involvement on turnover intention in the context of the implementation of advanced manufacturing technologies is not quite clear. For instance, Brown and Mitchell [29] support the claim that the work characteristics of JIT implementation could have detrimental effects on employees that would influence employee turnover while Schouteten and Benders [27] reported that employees in the lean production environment had low intention to resign. In the context of high-volume repetitive export-apparel manufacturing environment in Sri Lanka, prior to the implementation of lean production, employees engaged in routinized work and thus experienced low occurrence of operational problems to be solved. Hence, work was more monotonous and repetitive unlike after the implementation of the lean production where tasks consist of a coherent set of executing, preparing and supporting tasks with varying levels of difficulty. Therefore, the findings of our study suggest that when employees influence antecedents to work effort, such as goal setting and problem solving, their satisfaction and performance could enhance, which could reduce their turnover intention. This

implies that the level of lean implementation in the organisation may influence employee job involvement. That is, when lean production systems are fully implemented and when it becomes the standard operation in the production function, the lean production environment allows employees to actively involved in their jobs, for example, by root cause problem solving, exchange positions within the work group and giving each other a hand in moments of difficulty. Such job involvement reduces their turnover intention. However, as discussed in the limitations of the study, longitudinal studies are need to investigate any changes in this relationship over time to gain a deeper understanding. On the other hand, following the suggestions made by Schouteten and Benders [27], it is also possible to argue that the meagre labour market prospects play a role here. The operator level employees in the Sri Lankan industry tend to possess low formally recognized skills that are essential for finding higher qualified jobs [41, also refer to Table 1]. Yet, workforce statistics [36, 41] and past studies [42] report that the industry suffers with a monthly average turnover rate of 8% for shop-floor employees. In this context, the work environment of lean production may be perceived as an inducement for them to stay in their jobs.

It was found that job involvement mediates the relationship between POS and turnover intention. In other words, employees' global beliefs of being valued and cared for by the organisation enhance their job involvement, and job involvement in turn reduces their turnover intention in the lean production context. Overall, the literature on lean production mainly emphasize on aspects such as material delivery, reduced waste, and responsiveness of support personnel. However, the ways in which lean production environment influence employee behavior has received scant empirical attention. In this context, based on the organizational behavior theories we have developed a model to explain the

relationships between POS, job involvement and turnover intention in the lean production environment. Therefore, our study contributes to the operations management literature by viewing job involvement, which is a core characteristic of the lean production, as a salient mediator in the relationship between POS and employee turnover intention. Given that organisations desire their employees to exhibit high levels of job involvement and low levels of turnover intention, the provision of support is one of the viable mechanisms for enhancing job involvement and thereby reducing turnover intention. Therefore, organisations have to convey clear messages to employees that the organisation cares about its employees and values their contribution. Employees may consider increased job involvement, backed by being valued and supported by the organisation, as a positive experience in the organisation that reduces their intention to leave. Therefore, organisations aiming to increase employee job involvement may be able to tap into the various facets of employees' beliefs about organisational support to assess the extent of job involvement.

7 Limitations of the study and areas for future research

The limitations of this study should be acknowledged. First, although the literature provides evidence for different conceptualisations of job involvement, we have investigated one form of job involvement, i.e., participation. Second, although we intended to include constructs of lean production as controls in our model, we faced difficulties in collecting these data from all the firms that participated in the survey. Hence, we had to limit the variables that explain lean production to lean duration. Further, we have controlled five individual demographic variables in this study. Future research could investigate the influence of these variables on the relationship proposed in this study. Third, the

study was confined to the export-apparel industry in Sri Lanka. However, it should be noted that lean production practices are not yet well established in other industrial and service sectors compared to export-apparel industry in the country.

With regard to areas for future research, first, it should be noted, however, that we have not come across previous empirical studies that investigated the link proposed in this study in the context of lean production or advanced manufacturing systems to make straight forward comparisons. Therefore, more empirical work is needed to test our propositions and to replicate, extend, or disconfirm the results presented in this article. Second, future research could extend data collection by including managers, team leaders, human resource managers etc., who are actively involved in the lean production process; compliment questionnaire surveys with interviews and secondary data. Third, POS and job involvement may relate to other variables, such as job satisfaction, organisational citizenship behaviour, and organisational commitment. Therefore, future studies could extend the investigation by evaluating other variables of interest using path analysis techniques. Overall, individual work preferences could be assumed as unstable and context dependent. It is possible that, over time, employees may re-evaluate work arrangements and adapt to given situations, particularly when they perceive little alternative choice. Therefore, more research is needed on employees' attitudes towards both their jobs and the organisation itself in the context of advanced manufacturing systems.

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Figure

Fig.1 Hypothesized research model

Tables

Table 1 Characteristics of the sample (N=616)

Gender:		
Male		41%
Female		59%
Marital status:		
Single		64%
Married		36%
Age:		
Mean		25 yrs
S.D.		4.84
Tenure in the present workplace:		
Mean		4 yrs
S.D.		2.46
Highest level of education:		
Less than or equal G.C.E.(O/L)‡		67%
Up to G.C.E.(A/L)†		33%

Note: ‡General Certificate in Education (Ordinary Level) with 10 years of education.

†General Certificate in Education (Advanced Level) with 13 years of education.

Table 2 Correlations

	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1 Gender ^a	0.59	.49	1							
2 Age	0.49	.65	.096**	1						
3 Marital status ^a	0.65	.48	.032	-.389**	1					
4 Education ^a	0.49	.60	-.015	.035	.149**	1				
5 Tenure	2.93	.90	-.076*	.394**	-.170**	.105**	1			
6 Lean duration	2.15	.47	-.259**	-.006	-.151**	.009	.160**	1		
7. POS	3.93	.56	.106**	.046	-.065	.022	.005	.025	1	
8. Job involvement	4.09	.67	.143**	.113**	-.076	.011	.070*	.157**	.390**	1
9. Turnover intention	2.40	.65	.066	-.029	.096*	-.010	-.055	-.103**	-.367**	-.311**

Note. ** Significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed), * Significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed).

^a Binary-coded variables.

Table 3 Summarised results: regression analysis testing mediation on turnover intention

Step	Variable	B	S.E.	β	R ² (Adj.)	F
1	<i>Control variables^a</i>				.012	1.665
	Gender	.036	.078			
	Age	-.025	.069			
	Marital status	.080	.075			
	Education	.085	.061			
	Tenure	.026	.044			
	Lean duration	-.125	.077			
2	POS → Turnover intention	-.486	.061	-.433***	.178	10.835***
3	POS → Job involvement	.540	.071	.419***	.145	8.696***
4	POS → Turnover intention	-.375	.064	-.234**	.223	12.410***
	Job involvement → Turnover intention	-.205	.047	-.236***		

Sobel test $t = 3.783$ ($p = .000$); Aroian test $t = 3.759$ ($p = .000$); Goodman test $t = 3.805$ ($p = .000$)

Direct effect $\beta = -.134$; Indirect effect $\beta = -.233$

Note. ^a Control variables were retained in the subsequent steps of 2, 3, and 4.

** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$